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Impact Factor: 0.98

ASSESSING THE SAVING PATTERN OF DIFFERENT INCOME GROUP HOUSEHOLDS IN DISTRICT DAUSA, RAJASTHAN

Narendra Kumar Meena, Aruna Kaushik*

*Department of Economics, J. D. B., Girls Government College, Kota,
Rajasthan, India*

ABSTRACT

The present study aims at investigating the determinants of the saving behavior in different income group households in Dausa district, Rajasthan. The study is based on primary data collected from five hundred households, selected from five blocks of Dausa district. The results reveals that the age of the head of the household, occupation, family size, income and education are significantly influencing the saving behavior in the entire study area. We can see that large and rapid increase in income tends to raise the rate of household saving because households' capacity to save increases with household income. The estimate of total family size indicates that size of the household has negative relationship with saving of households, which means that if there is increase in household size then saving will be low and vice versa. On the other hand education has also negative effect on saving as educated household have higher consumption because they have to maintain a certain standard of living.

Key words: *Saving behavior, Income group, occupation, family size, education.*

Introduction:

From the classical times, saving has been considered as one of the determinants of growth. To lead the underdeveloped countries to the path of development, rate of savings must be enhanced. For the individuals and households, savings provide a cushion of security against future contingencies, whereas for the nation, savings provide the funds needed in the developmental efforts. To achieve higher rate of growth with relative price stability, the marginal propensity to save should be raised by appropriate incentives and policies. Also, in an era of international financial integration, for macro economic stability, higher domestic savings are essential (Gedela, 2012).

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Keynes (1936) identified absolute disposable income as the important determinant of saving. Other two post-keynesian theories, Friedman's (1957) Permanent Income Hypothesis (PIH) and Modigliani's (1963) Life Cycle Hypothesis (LCH) explains the determinants of savings point out that other variables also affect the saving of the households. Friedman (1957) PIH differentiated between permanent and transitory income and indicates that savings are influenced by both permanent and transitory income as well as present level of wealth (both human and non-human).

Saving is an important variable in the theory of economic growth. Several studies have been conducted to assess saving behaviour (Abid and Afridi, 2010). These studies include Qureshi (1981), Giovanni (1983), Ali (1985), Akhtar (1986), Khan (1988), Haque and Saleem (1991), Burney and Khan (1992), Siddique and Siddique (1993), Iqbal (1993), Sadaf (1994), Azhar (1995), Kazmi (1996), Hussein (1996), Khan and Nasir (1998), and Ayub (2001). Most of these studies have analyzed saving behaviour in overall Pakistan and then broken it down to the rural/urban level. In all these studies the effects of different variables like income, real and nominal rate of interest, rate of inflation, rate of growth of income, output rate, lagged output per capita, lagged population growth rate, foreign and domestic saving ratio, degeneracy ratio, age, education, employment status, earning status, occupation, purchase of jewellery, assets, imports, exports, foreign aid, bank credit, prime interest rate, workers' remittances, private capital outflows, expected inflation rate, development of financial institutions, residence location, secondary earner, sex, consumption pattern etc have been studied over saving pattern. The majority of the studies have used Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) to estimate the effects of all above different variables on saving behaviours.

Keeping in view the importance of the saving we conduct a research study to determine the effect of household savings. The main objectives of this study are to analyze the savings pattern of different income group households of Dausa District and also analyze the saving behavior of household with respect to education, family size and income source.

Materials and Methods:

The study was conducted to assess the households' savings pattern of different income group households of Dausa District, Rajasthan. A total sample of 500 households from five Block (Dausa, Lalsot, Baswa, Sikari & Mahwa) of Dausa district from each locality was randomly selected in 2014.

Keeping in view the objectives of the study a comprehensive questionnaire was developed. The questionnaire was pretested in the study area and modified according to the feedback. Single questionnaire was used to collect data on all aspects, regarding socioeconomic characteristics, consumption and saving pattern of the households.

Savings calculated was being obtained by the first definition of saving i.e. total monthly income minus total monthly expenditure.

Keynesian theory (1936) stated as there is positive relationship between income and saving. Duesenberry (1949) presented that consumption and saving is not only just related with absolute income but also related with relative income.

Results and Discussion:

Results of monthly average income, expenditure and saving of five income group family in Dausa district are given in Table 1. The standard deviation and coefficient of variation values of savings show that the variability of saving in different income groups was considerably very high. These household saving behaviour can be explained by various socio-economic factors along with income on household savings. The factors, whose impact on saving will be examined in this study are, education, family size and income.

Income, Expenditure and Saving: Table 1 shows the monthly average income, expenditure and saving of the sampled households. Minimum savings has been noticed in below 7500 Rs. income group while maximum savings above 80,000 Rs. income group. The relatively higher savings values are due to high income and low consumption.

Table 1: The monthly average income, expenditure and savings of the sampled households of five income group in Dausa district.

Income group (Rs.)	No. of households	Monthly average income	Monthly average consumption	Monthly average saving	Stdev. of saving	Coefficient of variation of saving
Below 7500	200	5346.65	5304.63	42.02	40.68	96.81
7500 to 16000	150	11954.11	10278.42	1675.69	1512.61	90.28
16000 to 80000	94	59261.69	19288.86	39972.83	24617.93	61.59
Above 80000	56	93987.50	36981.21	57006.29	18274.90	32.05

Source: Survey Data, 2014

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The positive and highly significant relationship between saving and disposable income reveals that as income of the people increases their saving also increases. According to Keynesian theory of consumption, there is positive relationship between income and saving. Our results matches with Keynesian theory of income and saving, as we can see in the above model that income has positive relationship with saving of the household. This shows that large and rapid increase in income tends to raise the rate of household saving because households' capacity to save increases with household income.

Socioeconomic Characteristics of Households:

The factors, whose impact on saving will be examined in this study are, education, family size and income source.

Education Level: Education can be defined as the process of developing knowledge, wisdom, and other desirable qualities of mind, character and general competency, especially by a source of formal instruction. Table 2 shows education level of the sampled households of Dausa district. The results indicate that out of 500 respondents only 4.60 percent were illiterate, 11.40 percent of the respondents were primary, 11.60 percent were secondary, 52.40 percent were educated up to degree (graduated or above graduated) and 20.00 percent were professional degree. The results also tell that the education rate in the low income group households was poor than high income group because low income group households can not pay fee of the colleges and universities.

Table 2: Education level of the sampled household in five income group of Dausa district.

Education level	Income group (Rs.)				Total	%
	Below 7500	7500 to 16,000	16,000 to 80,000	Above 80,000		
Illiterate	23 (11.50)	-	-	-	23	4.60
Primary	57 (28.50)	-	-	-	57	11.40
Secondary	32 (16.00)	23 (15.33)	03 (3.19)	-	58	11.60
Degree	76 (38.00)	92 (61.33)	67 (71.28)	27 (48.21)	262	52.40
Professional	12 (6.00)	35 (23.340)	24 (25.53)	29 (51.79)	100	20.00
Total	200	150	94	56	500	100

Source: Survey Data, 2014

Education is an important predictor for household behavior toward saving. The results tell us that education has negative effect on saving as educated household have higher consumption because they have to maintain a certain standard of living and usually spend more on children’s education, health, clothing, food and necessary luxury goods.

Family Size: According to India Demographic Survey a family or household can be defined as all those persons who usually live together and share their meal. Table 3 shows number of depended member of family of the sampled households of Dausa district. The results indicate that out of 500 respondents only 2.8 percent were zero, 4.6 percent of the respondents were one, 10.2 percent were two, 30.6 percent were three and 51.8 percent were above four depended member. The results also tell that depended member of family were increase then saving rate were decrease.

Table 3: Family size of the sampled household in five income group of Dausa district.

Number of family member	Income group (Rs.)				Total	%
	Below 7500	7500 to 16,000	16,000 to 80,000	Above 80,000		
0	03 (1.50)	07 (4.67)	02 (2.13)	02 (3.57)	14	2.80
1	07 (3.50)	08 (5.33)	04 (4.26)	04 (7.14)	23	4.60
2	11 (5.50)	15 (10.00)	17 (18.08)	08 (14.29)	51	10.20
3	76 (38.00)	29 (19.33)	30 (31.91)	18 (32.14)	153	30.60
Above 4	103 (51.50)	91 (60.67)	41 (43.62)	24 (42.86)	259	51.80
Total	200	150	94	56	500	100

Source: Survey Data, 2014

Negative and significant relationship between family size and saving is obviously stand true as family size increases most of the income would consume and less would be saved.

Source of Income: Income has been considered the most important factor in the determination of the saving behavior of an individual. More income means, normally, more saving and vice versa. Table 4 shows basic source of income of the sampled households of

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district Dausa. The result indicates that majority of the sampled respondents were involved in services/pension (34.80 percent) and in business (28.00 percent).

Table 4: Source of Income of the sampled household in five income group of Dausa district.

Source of Income	Income group (Rs.)				Total	%
	Below 7500	7500 to 16,000	16,000 to 80,000	Above 80,000		
Agriculture	69 (34.50)	28 (18.67)	09 (9.57)	.	106	21.20
Wages	56 (28.00)	21 (14.00)	03 (3.19)	.	80	16.00
Government service	34 (17.00)	42 (28.00)	47 (50.00)	32 (57.14)	155	31.00
Business	38 (19.00)	49 (32.67)	29 (30.85)	24 (42.86)	140	28.00
Pension	03 (1.50)	10 (6.66)	06 (6.39)	.	19	3.80
Total	200	150	94	56	500	100

Source: Survey Data, 2014

Saving sources of the sampled households: The role of savings in investment and therefore in development of a country can not be exaggerated. In developing country like India most of the saving is done by household. Table 5 represents the saving sources of the sampled households. The results show that most of the saving (68.80 percent) in the research area was through banks. On the other hand, 10.80 percent peoples save the money through cash. The results also show that 5.4, 4.6, 5.8 & 4.6 percent people saved the money through bonds, & others respectively.

Table 5: Saving Sources of the sampled household Sources in Dausa district.

Income group (Rs.)	Bank	Cash	Bonds	Share	Purchasing of the Physical Assets	Others	Total
Below 7500	178 (89.00)	05 (2.50)	09 (4.50)	02 (1.00)	04 (2.00)	02 (1.00)	200 .
7500 to 16,000	98 (65.33)	27 (18.00)	04 (2.67)	02 (1.33)	05 (3.33)	14 (9.34)	150 .
16,000 to 80,000	44 (46.81)	14 (14.90)	08 (8.51)	09 (9.57)	13 (13.83)	06 (6.38)	94 .
Above 80,000	24 (42.86)	08 (14.29)	06 (10.71)	10 (17.86)	07 (12.50)	01 (1.78)	56 .
Total	344	54	27	23	29	23	500
%	68.80	10.80	5.40	4.60	5.80	4.60	100

Source: Survey Data, 2014

Conclusions and Recommendations:

In this study we have analyzed the saving behavior of household in urban and rural areas of District Dausa, Rajasthan. For the empirical analysis, we have constructed the effect of income, family size and education on saving of households. From the analysis we see that

saving is strongly effected by the above proposed variables. Further the results indicates that income has positive effect on saving behavior of household whereas education and family size have negative effect on saving of the household in District Dausa.

Savings are essential component of growing economy. From our analysis it is found that household savings are discouraged in study areas and there is need to improve household savings, which is possible by the government support. Government can increase saving in the study area through following steps: i) by creating job opportunities to individuals of the rural areas as well as the educated persons in District Dausa; ii) by subsidizing the general price level at its optimal level; iii) by providing free educational facilities to the people of the area.

Acknowledgements:

The authors are thankful to University Grants Commission, New Delhi for Rajiv Gandhi Fellowship sanctioned to Mr. Narendra Kumar Meena for this work.

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